

Recommended citation: Wiley, K. (2018). The use of self and peer review to engage students with assessment criteria, develop their judgement and critical evaluation skills and extend the benefit of instructor feedback. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 512-519). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672609.

SELF AND PEER REVIEW TO ENGAGE STUDENTS WITH ASSESSMENT CRITERIA, DEVELOP THEIR JUDGEMENT AND CRITICAL EVALUATION SKILLS AND EXTEND THE BENEFITS OF INSTRUCTOR FEEDBACK.

K. Willey

Faculty of Engineering and Information Technologies
The University of Sydney
Camperdown, Sydney, Australia
E-mail: keith.willey@sydney.edu.au

Keywords: self and peer assessment, Collaborative learning, Academic standards

1 INTRODUCTION

While assessment may shape students' perception of learning [1], to be effective learners, students need to understand the assessment processes, criteria being used and the learning outcomes being assessed [2]. Many activities have been designed to assist students to engage with and understand assessment processes including providing written criteria and grade descriptors. However, this is frequently not sufficient to make what is often tacit 'knowledge' visible to students. It could be argued that this is particularly relevant for students new to higher education who are yet to have become familiar with the learning culture and expectations of the institution in which they are studying. We suggest that for students to be socialised into these tacit assessment standards and practices they need opportunities to practice and receive feedback.

This paper reports how students behaved and responded to a self and peer review activity aimed at developing student's judgement, appreciation and understanding of academic standards to increase the benefits from assessment in a first year engineering program.

2 BACKGROUND

Boud [3] argues that learning is socially and culturally constructed by the learner. But a social construction requires a language allowing students to think about, understand and discuss their learning. The same attributes are also required for students to develop their professional judgement.

Many activities have been designed to assist students to engage with and understand assessment processes ranging from the arguably mandatory written criteria and grade descriptors linked to learning outcomes through to providing summative feedback tasks and collaborative discussions. However, this is often not sufficient to make academic standards, which are often tacit 'knowledge', visible to students [4].

Many academics and universities assume that a students' ability to make academic judgements will automatically develop as they compare their assessments with those of expert instructors and tutors. However, academics often use holistic judgement which they subsequently justify by resort to criteria [5]. Sadler recommends that students should move beyond 'teacher-supplied feedback to learner self-monitoring' requiring instructors to design explicit opportunities for students to develop and evaluate their expertise. He suggests that self-evaluative skills need to be developed 'by providing direct authentic evaluative experience for students' [5] (p. 119) such as making judgements about work they have completed. Rust introduces the analogy of developing 'connoisseurship', which is largely about socialisation and experience "involving observation, imitation, dialogue and practice" [4] (p. 152).

Self-regulation as described by Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick [6] requires students to be able to effectively judge their own work. Without such ability students learning will be less effective and they will be unable to judge whether their approaches to learning and chosen methods of study are effective and appropriate [7]. This development of judgement is extremely important not only for students learning but in their professional practice. For example, using judgement and being able to develop judgement is required to evaluate if their contribution, work, analysis et cetera is sufficient to meet the requirements of workplace tasks undertaken [8].

Sadler identified three conditions for feedback to effectively influence learning:

1. a knowledge of the standards
2. having to compare those standards to one's own work, and
3. taking action to close the gap between the two [5] (p. 138).

In this paper we focus on using self, peer and academic review to improve student's judgement. The University of Sydney reports the main aims of self and peer assessment are to [9]:

1. increase student responsibility and autonomy
2. strive for a more advanced and deeper understanding of the subject matter, skills and processes
3. lift the role and status of the student from passive learner to active learner and assessor (this also encourages a deeper approach to learning)
4. involve students in critical reflection
5. develop in students a better understanding of their own subjectivity and judgement.

Learning activities should be also scaffolded to reduce undesirable anxiety, promote engagement and ensure students understand and hence can benefit from the learning opportunity provided. Willey and Gardner [10] recommend that academics should explain to students:

- why they designed the assessment activity the way they did,
- what learning opportunities the activity provides the students,
- how students can evaluate their learning from the activity, and
- how it is going to impact on their reality (enable them to see the world differently).

The last step being arguably the most important. If students are not gaining something from our learning activities that enables them to see the world differently, provide a different perspective or new awareness then we are only confirming what they already knew.

We suggest that for students to be socialised into the often tacit assessment standards and practices, they need opportunities to practice and receive feedback and that, it is important to commence this socialisation in the first year of their studies.

This paper reports on the impact of a self and peer review activity in developing student's judgement, developing an appreciation and understanding of academic standards and increasing the benefits from assessment in a first year engineering subject.

3 STUDY

The described activity involves student's self and peer reviewing their own and each other's assessment artefacts. Students are required to grade the artefacts against criteria and provide feedback explaining their decisions. Typically, students self-assess their own work and peer assess the work of two others. This reduces what I call writing for the tutor, a process by which a student's work is only ever seen by them self and the tutor and the tutors feedback only has an impact on the student who submitted the work. In the described self and peer review process students get to see the judgements and feedback from them self, two peers, and the tutor for three (their own and two peers) submissions.

In the reported instance aliases were used to provide students with anonymity while still identifying whether the feedback and ratings were provided by a student or an instructor. For example, the aliases for students were assessor 1, assessor 2, assessor 3 et cetera and for the instructors, tutor 1, tutor 2 et cetera (in previous trials students were identified). The same alias was used for all three reviews (self and two peers) allowing the ratings and comments provided by a particular student (assessor) or instructor (tutor) to be recognised (see Fig 1). This facilitated students identifying the different standards applied, for example, some students were characterised as being hard or easy markers. The activity was designed to build

students professional skills including judgement and critical evaluation while simultaneously building their understanding of academic standards.

Facilitating self and peer assessment can result in significant academic workload and is almost unsustainable in large classes without the assistance of some form of educational technology. SPARK^{PLUS} [11] [12] is used to support the self and peer review process discussed in this paper.

4 CONTEXT

A large (>500 enrolments) multidisciplinary first year engineering subject was chosen for this study.

As part of their assessment students had to undertake a group design project. The narrative used to scaffold the design project had student working as teams of interns for a fictitious company. At the end of the semester students had to apply for a part time design engineer position with the company. This required them to write a cover letter and respond to two of the selection criteria. The selection criteria were taken from actual advertisements for engineering positions and were chosen to reflect the professional development required by the discipline and recognised in accordance with Engineers Australia level I competencies [13]. To assist them in preparing their application students were required to maintain a portfolio within which they planned, monitored and evaluated their development of the skills listed in the selection criteria.

While the student peer reviews had no impact on the grade a student received for their submitted job application (this was determined solely by the tutor) students were given marks for each of their peer reviews.

Awarding marks for the quality of the peer reviews fits well with the subject learning objective to develop critical evaluation and assessment skills. It also motivated students to engage, participate and provide quality peer reviews. We felt this was particularly important being a first year unit. In later years when students have become familiar with self and peer review processes and the learning opportunities they provide these review activities are formative.

4.1 What students see

The results screen allows students to compare their ratings and written feedback/reasoning against each of the assessment criterion to that of their student peers and tutors for each submission they assessed (Fig 1)

Participants can also view a summary of their ratings for different submissions to compare their ratings (grades used FA: Fail, P: pass, C: credit, D: distinction, HD: high distinction) with those of their fellow assessors. This comparison can be self against all the other assessors or just against student peers, tutors/instructors or any other category using the drop-down menu (Fig 2).

OVERALL QUALITY OF COVER LETTER

How well the applicant addressed the listed knowledge, skills and attributes in their cover letter

Level of persuasiveness/influencing. How much did the cover letter make you want to employ the applicant?

Briefly explain the reasons for your rating and indicate both what was well done and the issues you consider need the most improvement.

OVERALL QUALITY OF RESPONSE TO SELECTION CRITERIA

How well the applicant addressed the selection criteria

How well the applicant used evidence to support their claimed experience/skill level

Briefly explain the reasons for your rating and indicate both what was well done and the issues you consider need the most improvement.

▼ Natalie Fawcett Rating
 ▲ Tutor1 Rating
 ▲ Assessor19 Rating
 ▲ Assessor2 Rating
 ▲ Assessor14 Rating

Student's (self) rating of their submission

Peer and tutor ratings of submission see key below

Comments of participants (in this case self, peers and tutor)

Key to identify who made each rating (this is as Natalie would view the results hence she is identified while the other assessors are de-identified)

Fig 1: Multiple Assessor results screen. Students enter their ratings and feedback individually before viewing the results (SPARK^{PLUS} also facilitates the assessors to be identified).

Select Alias: All Aliases Combined | Show your ratings

Sort on: Group rating | Your rating

Show ratings as: Numbers | Labels | Bars | Show Histograms

Name (# assessors)	Overall quality of presentation and layout	Overall quality of writing	Overall quality of cover letter	Overall Quality of response to selection criteria
T10A Assessor 15	DI-	CR-	DI-	DI
T10A Assessor 9	DI	DI+	DI	HD-
T10A Assessor 16	DI	DI	CR+	CR

Your Rating

Average rating of peers

Submission

Fig 2: Multiple Assessor comparative summary screen.

Select Alias: All Aliases Split | Show your ratings

Sort on: Group rating | Your rating

Show ratings as: Numbers | Labels | Bars | Show Histograms

Name (# assessors)	Overall quality of presentation and layout			Overall quality of writing			Overall quality of cover letter			Overall Quality of response to selection criteria		
	*Assessor	Assessor	Tutor	*Assessor	Assessor	Tutor	*Assessor	Assessor	Tutor	*Assessor	Assessor	Tutor
T10A Assessor 15	HD+	DI-	PS	HD-	CR-	PS+	HD	DI-	FA+	HD	DI	FA
T10A Assessor 16	CR	DI	CR	DI	DI	HD	CR	CR+	DI	PS	CR	CR
T10A Assessor 9	DI	CR+	CR	DI+	DI	CR	DI	DI	CR+	HD-	PS+	DI-

Your Rating

Self (author's) Rating

Average rating of peers

Tutor Rating

Fig 3: Multiple Assessor comparative summary screen.

Alternatively, it is possible to split the summary screen to compare your ratings to the average rating provided by each of the assigned assessor groups. In this case we categorised students as assessors and instructors as tutors (Fig 3)

5 RESULTS

92 students from a cohort of 520 agreed to answer a series of questions and describe their learning experience from the self and peer review process. 78% of these students reported that having to peer review job applications of other students and subsequently being able to compare their own, their peers and their tutor's assessments and feedback had improved their capacity to write as a professional. 77% of participating students said the process improved their understanding and awareness of how to improve their professional skills through:

the opportunity provided by the activity design;

"THIS WAS ALSO A VERY WELL structured component of the Job Application. It was very effective in developing critical evaluation and feedback skills. It enabled students to examine how other applications had pros and cons and where each application could improve aspects they lacked in".

"It helped me find out what I need to improve, and gave me a chance to compare myself with others".

The reviews *"told me where I should improve and some professional advice was also useful"*

comparing one's own submission with other students;

"I think that the peer reviewing was helpful to see how other people write and seeing where they went wrong to improve in those areas for the future".

"I saw some mistakes in other people's writing and then thought back to my own work and realised some of the mistakes I had also been making in my work so it was an eye-opener to not only the flaws of my peers but also to my own".

having to assess and provide feedback on someone else's submission;

"I found writing the feedback more helpful than the feedback itself. It allows you to contrast someone's work to your own and make judgement on things you did well and ways you could both improve".

the tutor assessment and feedback,

"By comparing with others and get feedback from them and tutor, I can directly see the weakness of my job application.

Despite the fact that tutors also provided assessments in line with findings by Sampson and Cohen [14] some student's perceived peer learning as having little value as feedback is often not given by a recognised expert.

“Not many peer students actually know what is a good cover letter including myself, so it is hard to make judgement and comments as to evaluate others comment and make an improvement”.

“I found that the feedback from my peers differed wildly - both from themselves and from the tutor. This meant that I became more uncertain as to how I did”.

This activity has been run for a number of semesters on some occasions both the person who submitted the work and the reviewers were anonymised on others the identity of both the submitting student and the reviewers was known. The activity was successful in both instances although some students did appreciate the anonymity when it was provided.

A preliminary analysis also uncovered evidence to support Boud's study [8] that found compared to instructor judgements lower ability students significantly overestimated their ability in self assessments, while higher ability students often underestimated their grades. This supports our belief in having assessment groups made up of students of different abilities. It allows the lower achieving student to receive feedback from higher achieving student and an opportunity for higher achieving student to articulate their judgement, critical evaluation and understanding (if a high achieving student is assessing a high achieving student there is often less opportunity to provide critical evaluation).

5.1 Improving Learning Culture and Practice

A variation of this activity to assist students to make the most out of learning activities is to ask students to answer a number of questions and provide feedback about how they have engaged with and/or approached a learning activity. Once the results are published students are encouraged to compare their experiences using the result histograms and view the comments of students who have rated the activity at different levels of satisfaction. For example, a student who rated a learning activity as poor often finds a more beneficial way of engaging with, and learning from, these activities by reading the comments from students that rated the activity as good or excellent. This student feedback also helps instructors to improve both the design and scaffolding of their learning activities.

6 CONCLUSION / FURTHER INTEGRATION

The self and peer review activities involving students and instructors provided a valuable opportunity for students to evaluate, receive feedback on and develop their critical evaluation and assessment skills and their understanding of academic standards. We have now incorporated into our second, third and fourth year subject's formative opportunities to undertake this type of assessment. In these subjects we have also included opportunities for groups to collaborate to assess other groups and extended the assessed activities to include in addition to written submissions, oral presentations, engineering designs and critical evaluations.

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